

THE EFFECT OF USING A CONDITIONER TO REMOVE THE SMEAR LAYER FROM THE SURFACE OF ROOT DENTIN ON THE ADHESION OF GLASS IONOMER CEMENTS**Gurbanov R.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
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Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14332309>**Abstract**

Dental filling; is the final stage of endodontic treatment, to which great importance is attached. Necessity and; the importance of high-quality dental filling is justified by: results;; statistical and epidemiological research; In general - in. In the structure of dental care*, inflammatory processes of the pulp and periodontium account for over 30%. Moreover, the number of patients with acute and chronic diseases of the dental system is constant; growing.

Keywords: root canal treatment, glass ionomer cement.

In dental practice, glass ionomer cements (GICs) are used for various purposes, including filling root canals and fixing fixed orthopedic structures [1, 4, 10]. The durability of the restoration and the prognosis of treatment results are largely determined by both the strict adherence to instructions and the sequence of clinical manipulations, and other reasons, one of which is the adhesion of GIC to dentin. Adhesion is the result of intermolecular interaction, ionic or metallic bonding [5]. It depends not only on the properties of the filling material, but also on the nature of the preparation of the surface layers of dentin immediately before filling [2, 6, 9]. Adhesion is measured by the pull-off force per unit area of contact between surfaces and becomes extremely large with full contact over the entire area of contact between the bodies [3, 5]. GIC forms exclusively chemical bonds with dental hard tissues, mainly due to polyacrylic acid, which is part of the liquid [9]. After tooth preparation, a smear layer forms on the surface of the dentin, preventing the formation of these chemical bonds. Preliminary use of a weak solution of polyacrylic acid (10–20%), which is the main component of the conditioner, allows you to remove the smear layer from the dentin surface [11]. Within 10 seconds, this relatively weak acid dissolves the smear layer. Its exposure for more than 20 s causes demineralization of dentin and unclogs dentinal tubules. With open dentinal tubules, it is likely that dentinal fluid will leak out, which may subsequently affect the adhesion of GIC [9]. In pulpless teeth, the duration of conditioning can be increased, which allows the dentinal tubules to open and create conditions for additional retention. It is possible to use the drug EDTA, which, like phosphoric, citric or polyacrylic acids, is able to remove the smear layer and open the dentinal tubules [12]. Since GIC liquid consists of acid, its use can also achieve this goal. Considering all of the above, the purpose of this work was to study the effect of additional treatment of root dentin with various preparations on the adhesion of GIC, which is

important for improving the fixation of intra-root post structures. The objectives of the work were to determine the amount of adhesion of GIC to dentin when treating it with: conditioner, EDTA, GIC liquid and to compare the amount of adhesion of GIC to dentin without special treatment. As samples imitating the hard tissues of human teeth and having a microstructure close to them, extracted intact single-rooted bovine teeth were taken (according to ISO technical requirements) [7]. The teeth were trepanned, depulped, and instrumental root canal treatment was performed. During all manipulations, the teeth were constantly moistened. The roots of the selected teeth, similar in size and shape, were sawn into separate segments with a thickness of 2 mm. A total of 40 samples were received. To unify the experimental conditions, the lumen of the root canal of each sample was calibrated to the same size (2 mm in diameter). All samples were divided into four groups (three experimental and one control) of 10 samples each. Ketac Molar GIC (3M ESPE) was used for filling in all cases. Dentin preparation was carried out as follows: • Conditioning. Applying Conditioner Bond PSP (GB) to dentin, exposure for 15 s, rinsing with water, drying (without overdrying), filling with GIC according to the instructions. • EDTA treatment. • application of EDTA FILE-Eze (Ultradent, USA), exposure 15 minutes, rinsing with water, drying, filling with GIC. • Treatment with Ketac Molar liquid (3M ESPE). Apply Ketac Molar liquid to the dentin for 15 s, remove excess with paper turunda, and fill with GIC.

In the control group, GIC filling was carried out without prior special preparation of dentin. After filling, all samples were stored in distilled water at +40C (ISO requirements) [7]. During the experimental study, each sample was subjected to a load using an experimental universal installation INSTRON 1195 (Fig. 1), where a load was applied to the filling material through the punch of the device at a speed of 1 mm/min (Fig. 2). The GIC was squeezed out into the cuvette

cavity located under the sample. In order to reduce the likelihood of a rupture in the filling material itself, the transverse dimensions of the punch were as close as possible to the diameter of the filling (GRC) in the sample. The increase in load was recorded on an electronic display and additionally recorded by a recorder on calibrated paper in the form of a curve. The moment of rupture in the dentin-GIC system was indicated by a sharp decline in the increasing curve and the display of the corresponding value on the electronic display. The magnitude of the pull-out resistance force was expressed in kgf. Based on the data obtained in each group, the arithmetic mean and its mean error were calculated. The results obtained are presented in the table. The results obtained show that without dentin treatment, the peel resistance force is 11.34–1.3 kgf, and with additional treatment with conditioner, GIC adhesion increases significantly (by 30%) and is equal to 14.96 ±1.8 kgf. The experimentally detected increase in GIC adhesion when treating dentin with EDTA (12.34±1.4 kgf) and a slight weakening when treating with Ketac Molar liquid (10.31±1.87 kgf) probably require additional study due to the low levels of different results .

Conclusion.

Thus, as a result of the experiment, it was revealed that the use of a conditioner to remove the smear layer from the surface of root dentin increases the adhesion force of GIC by 30%, which is important when fixing intraroot post structures with glass ionomer cements.

References:

1. Getman N.V. Sravnitel'naja ocenka razlichnyh fiksirujushhih materialov pri ispol'zovanii ankerov. Osnovnye napravlenija razvitija stomatologii v RB: Sb. materialov. Mn.: BelMAPO 2003; 30–32.
2. Dudko A.S. // Medicinskie novosti. — 1996. — №4. — S. 29–32.
3. Nikolaenko S.A. //Stomatologija. — 2003. — №5. — S. 8–11.
4. Polonejchik N.M., Myshkovec N.A., Getman N.V. Fiksirujushhie materialy dlja nes#emnyh zubnyh protezov. — Minsk, 2002.
5. Prohorov A.M., Alekseev D.M., Bonch-Bruevich A.M., Borovik-Romanov A.S. Fizicheskiy jenciklopedicheskiy slovar'. Sov. Jenciklopedija. — 1983. — S. 11–12.